

Readiness and problems encountered by teachers on the opening of the school year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19: an analysis

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ABSTRACT

The readiness of the teachers on the opening of classes and the way they address the problems they encounter are crucial especially in times of crisis like COVID-19. To dive into this issue, I conducted a study with a focus on the problems encountered by teachers in Binulasan Integrated School in the Philippines on the opening of School Year 2020-2021. The aim of this research was also to propose an intervention scheme. I used a complete enumeration or census method in the study, employing the descriptive-quantitative method. The results revealed that the teachers possessed a positive outlook towards their profession and claimed that they are ready to perform their duties and responsibilities under the new normal engendered by the COVID-19 pandemic. This readiness was verbally expressed as "Highly Ready" and is reflected in the overall mean score of 3.46. Meanwhile, most of the problems encountered by the teachers were considered not as serious problems, which was verbally interpreted as "Problem is Slightly Serious" as reflected by the overall mean score of 1.80. A concern was, however, shown on the delayed distribution of printed modules, which they could have studied first before imparting efficiently to their pupils. Also, teachers seemed to be having a hard time budgeting their time in doing their tasks while watching webinars given by the Department of Education. Lastly, the teachers seemed unhappy with the lack of supply of Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs) and face masks even though they are required to conduct a house-to-house distribution of the modules to the learners. This implies that teachers may utilize the intervention program proposed in this paper, which was designed to address and overcome the problems they encountered on the opening of classes due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

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1. Introduction

The 1987 Constitution of the Philippines, Section 1 Article 14 mandates that "the state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels" and section 2 of Republic Act No. 10533 otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 which states that "the State shall establish, maintain and support a complete, adequate and integrated system of education relevant to the

needs of the people, the country and society-at-large". Hence, teachers play a vital role in realizing these provisions to provide quality education to all.

On the same note, DepEd Order No. 42, series of 2017 otherwise known as the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers which states that "Teachers play a crucial role in nation-building. Through quality teachers, the Philippines can develop holistic learners who are steeped in values, equipped with 21st-century skills, and able to propel the country to development and progress" Hence, enhancing teacher quality becomes of utmost importance for long-term and sustainable nation-building.

However, these provisions in the 21st-century education seem to be challenged since most governments around the world have temporarily closed educational institutions in an attempt to contain the spread of the CoVid-19 pandemic. (UNESCO, 2020)

In a separate statement, UNESCO (2020), stated that in such unprecedented and uncertain times, it is normal for people to experience a higher level of stress and anxiety, including the teachers. They further said that teachers need supports to face the extra pressure being put on them to deliver learning in a time of crisis as well as support their students' needs. Hence, it is very important to assess the teachers' readiness in providing quality education to the learners.

With the current situation mentioned above, the researcher attempted to determine the readiness and the problems encountered by the teachers in Binulasan Integrated School on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19 and to provide an intervention scheme.

2. Research Questions

This action research aimed to determine the teachers' readiness and the problems encountered by teachers in Binulasan Integrated School on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 and to propose an intervention scheme. Specifically, this action research sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the level of teachers' readiness on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19?
2. What are the problems encountered by the teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19?
3. Is there a significant difference to the teachers' readiness and the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19?
4. Based on the findings of this action research, what Intervention Scheme may be designed for the teachers in Binulasan Integrated School?

3. Hypothesis

There is no significant difference to the readiness and the problems encountered by the teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19.

4. A brief review of related literature and studies

This chapter presents the related literature and studies coming from various authors that helped the researcher in conceptualizing ideas to the present study. The researcher used thematic organization of ideas which is considered as comprehensive, scholarly, systematic and easy to utilize (Aque, 2014).

4.1 Teachers' Readiness

Moreno and Gortazar (2020), conducted a study about schools' readiness for digital learning as a response to the educational crisis brought by CoVid-19 and found out that principals were reasonably positive towards the teachers' readiness in using the digital devices available, with quite a few countries reaching 90 percent and higher. Their findings also speak that most school principals are quite confident about the pedagogical skills possessed by their teachers and the availability of resources to help them use digital learning while students remain at home.

On the other hand, in the study of Brooks and Grajek (2020), they found out that teachers, although being skilled educators, have various reasons not to utilize online teaching. One of the reasons that faculty don't want to teach online is that they don't believe it helps students learn effectively. Despite overwhelming empirical evidence demonstrating the efficacy of online learning, only 21% of faculty agree that online learning can help students learn effectively.

They recommended that institutions should utilize the opportunity to educate their faculty about the efficacy of online teaching and learning and to support their efforts to transition and teach their courses online. At the same time, institutions should be prepared to manage potential resistance and backlash. If successful, institutions could shift the viewpoints of faculty who disagree that online teaching environments do enable students' learning

Also, Malipot (2020), reported that a teachers' group expressed their support to the proposed revision of the school calendar in the Philippines, noting that this would provide flexibility to the authorities to determine the date of opening of classes during the times of emergency such as the COVID-19 pandemic. With this, Teachers' Dignity Coalition National Chairperson Benjo Basas quoted that *"The reality is, we are not prepared or perhaps we need a little more time to prepare"*

However, despite the pandemic issues and concerns, he also said that teachers are always ready to do their duties. He added that as he has said in the past that as long as the safety of school personnel and learners is ensured, these dedicated teachers will gladly comply as they are patiently doing different tasks, virtual and physical even during the Community Quarantine period.

4.2 Problems Encountered

Kurtz (2020), found that there are some problems encountered by the teachers during this pandemic. He said that, since online teaching was utilized already in some schools across the globe, students' and teachers' morale is down. Saying that whatever it is, the reality is that student and teacher morale is suffering (as reported

by teachers and district leaders), declining considerably between March 25 and April 8. In March, the teachers and district leaders which were surveyed reported that morale was lower than before the pandemic for 61 percent of students and 56 percent of teachers.

Another challenge is the usage of social media platforms to communicate when teachers interact with students, it's most likely to occur via email. A majority also communicate by posting written messages online, and through online communications or video conferencing platforms. The use of Zoom has raised some big student data privacy and security issues, prompting a growing number of districts to prohibit the use of Zoom for school-related business. So far, though, most educators have not experienced problems. Just 16 percent of teachers and district leaders say someone in their district has been "Zoombomb" on Zoom or a similar video conferencing platform. He also pointed out that more than a fifth of students are not participating in school, with larger truancy rates in high-poverty communities. Even as teachers do communications and instruction, they reported that, on average, 21 percent of their students are essentially "truant" during coronavirus closures (not logging in, not making contact, etc.) The percentages are highest among districts in which more than three-quarters of students are from low-income families. Nearly 1 in 3 students in those communities are not participating in remote learning, compared with 12 percent in districts in which a quarter or fewer students live in poverty.

Lastly, he cited that schools don't have a finished and concrete plan if the crisis continues. Since it is certainly possible that the coronavirus pandemic will continue or recur in the 2020-2021 school year. But just 7 percent of district leaders said they have a thorough and extensive plan for moving forward if that happens. However, close to half say they have at least started planning for that possibility.

5. Theoretical Framework

This action research was anchored on the theory of John Watson's Behavioral Theory, also known as the behavioral psychology. It is a theory of learning based on the idea that all behaviors are acquired through conditioning. Wherein, this conditioning occurs through [interaction with the environment](#). Behaviorists believe that our responses to environmental stimuli shape someone's actions. (Cherry, 2019)

Meanwhile, the above-mentioned theory was applied in assessing the teachers' readiness on how they handle the present situation while doing their duties and responsibilities as well as to determine the problems they encountered during this pandemic.

**Readiness and Problems Encountered by Teachers in
Binulasan Integrated School
On the Opening of School Year 2020-2021 Due to CoVid-19**

Figure 1. The Research Paradigm.

6. Scope and Limitations

This action research was limited to all elementary teachers in Binulasan Integrated School, Infanta, Quezon-Philippines. Its main concern was to determine the teachers' readiness and the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19 and to provide an intervention scheme.

7. Research Methodology

7.1 Research Design

The researcher utilized a quantitative research that employed a descriptive research design. A descriptive research design is a valid method for researching specific subjects and as a precursor to more quantitative studies (Shuttlesworth, 2008). To

achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher utilized a questionnaire as the main instrument of the study. The researcher analyzed and interpreted the data gathered using an appropriate statistical treatment.

7.2 Research Locale

This study was conducted in Binulasan Integrated School located in Brgy. Binulasan Infanta, Quezon. The researcher used this locale because it is the school where he teaches.

7.3 The Respondents

The present study utilized a complete enumeration. Hence, all elementary teachers in Binulasan Integrated School except the researcher himself were included. Hence, there were 34 teachers that served as the respondents of this study.

7.4 Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought first the permission to his school head before he determined the teachers' readiness and the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19. After securing all the necessary communication with respective authorities, the researcher distributed the questionnaire through messenger (online) due to the current situation. The data gathered were treated using statistical tools.

7.5 Research Instrument

The researcher constructed a researcher-made questionnaire that served as the main tool in the present study which was answered through messenger (online). It was a 20-item survey questionnaire that covered items to determine the teachers' readiness (10) and the problems they encountered (10) on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19. The validation of the survey questionnaire was conducted in Binulasan Integrated School - Junior High School Department. The data gathered from the dry-run was subjected to a statistic Pearson Product Moment Correlation other known as the Pearson r to determine the coefficient of correlation (r). The computed coefficient of correlation which was 0.91 confirmed that the survey instrument was very highly reliable and valid.

7.8 Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used to interpret the data gathered.

1. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r). This was used to test the reliability and validity of the survey instrument. Also, this was used in determining the relationship between the teachers' readiness and the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19. This Pearson r finds the degree of association of two sets of variables.

The formula is:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2][N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Where:

- r_{xy} = correlation between X and Y
- X = sum of test X
- Y = sum of test Y
- XY = sum of the product of X and Y
- N = number of cases
- X^2 = sum of squared X scores
- Y^2 = sum of squared Y scores

2. Weighted Mean. This was used in analyzing the level of the teachers' readiness as well as the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19. This is an average calculated by taking into account not only the frequencies of the values of a variable but also another factor such as the variance, the formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Where:

- WM = Weighted Mean
- $\sum x$ = summation of weighted frequencies
- N = number of cases

To interpret the results of the teachers' readiness on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19, the scale below was used:

3.50-4.00	Highly Ready
2.50-3.49	Ready
1.50-2.49	Slightly Ready
1.00-1.49	Not Ready

Meanwhile, to interpret the problems encountered by the teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19, the scale below was used:

3.50-4.00	Problem is Very Serious
2.50-3.49	Problem is Serious
1.50-2.49	Problem is Slightly Serious
1.00-1.49	Not a Problem at All

8. Results and discussion

This chapter covers the results and discussion concerning the teachers' readiness and problems encountered by teachers in Binulasan Integrated School on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19 as well as the proposed Intervention

Scheme. The order of the discussion followed the arrangement of the Specific Questions in Chapter 1.

Specific Question No.1 What is the level of the teachers' readiness on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19?

Specific Question No.1 What is the level of teachers' readiness on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19?

Table 1
Teachers' Readiness

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1	The school head had oriented the teachers regarding the new normal as a preparation on the opening of School Year 2020-2021.	3.68	Highly Ready	2
2	The school head prepared various plans, safety measures, alternatives and interventions to ensure the health of teachers and learners during the distribution of modules to every learners.	3.71	Highly Ready	1
3	The teacher is well-informed about the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) they will be utilizing to the learners.	3.60	Highly Ready	3
4	The teacher is ready and knowledgeable enough in initiating the new normal in teaching the learners.	3.31	Ready	8
5	The teacher is ready in conducting home visitations and to the distribution of modules and other learning materials to the learners (house to house)	3.44	Ready	6
6	The teacher is ready to apply and execute those learnings he/she has learned from various online seminars/lectures initiated by the Department of Education.	3.46	Ready	5
7	The teacher had prepared and initiated innovations as a result from listening and participating webinars conducted by the Department of Education	3.27	Ready	9
8	The teacher is physically and emotionally ready on the opening of School Year 2020-2021.	3.40	Ready	7
9	The teacher is ready on the evaluation of the pupils' learning and outputs through utilizing various assessments.	3.26	Ready	10
10	The teacher is ready to supplement the pupils' learning through effective reinforcements and interventions.	3.49	Ready	4
	Average Weighted Mean	3.46	Ready	

Table 1 presents the weighted means, verbal interpretations, and ranks on the readiness of teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021. As shown above, among ten categories, three of them had verbal interpretations as "Highly Ready". "The school head had prepared various plans, safety measures, alternatives, and interventions to ensure the health of teachers and learners during the distribution of modules to every learner" ranked 1 with a weighted mean of 3.71. "The school head had oriented the teachers regarding the new normal as a preparation on the opening of School Year 2020-2021" ranked 2 with a weighted mean of 3.68. "The teacher is well-informed about the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) they will be utilizing to the learners" ranked 3 with a weighted mean of 3.60.

Meanwhile, seven categories had verbal interpretations as "Ready" such as "The teacher is ready to supplement the pupils' learning through effective reinforcements and interventions" which ranked 4 with 3.49 as its weighted mean. Ranked 5 had a weighted mean of 3.46 which is "The teacher is ready to apply and execute those learnings he/she has learned from various online seminars/lectures initiated by the Department of Education". "The teacher is ready in conducting home

visitations and to the distribution of modules and other learning materials to the learners (house to house)" ranked 6 with a weighted mean of 3.44.

A weighted mean of 3.40 ranked 7 which is "The teacher is physically and emotionally ready on the opening of School Year 2020-2021.". Ranked 8 is "The teacher is ready and knowledgeable enough in initiating the new normal in teaching the learners." With a weighted mean of 3.31. Ranked 9 is "The teacher had prepared and initiated innovations as a result from listening and participating webinars conducted by the Department of Education" had a weighted mean of 3.27. While "the teacher is ready on the evaluation of the pupils' learning and outputs through utilizing various assessments." Ranked 10 with a weighted mean of 3.26. In general, the teachers' readiness in Binulasan Integrated School had a score of 3.46 which is interpreted as "Ready"

As disclosed, all the indicators were interpreted as "Ready" except to the school head had prepared oriented the teachers in their upcoming tasks to the new normal, prepared safety measures and interventions to ensure the health of teachers and learners during the distribution of modules to every learner as well as the teachers' knowledge towards the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) which were verbally interpreted as "Highly Ready". This may mean that despite this pandemic, teachers are always ready in doing their duties and responsibilities. This finding is supported by Malipot (2020) as he cited the Teachers' Dignity Coalition National Chairperson, Mr. Benjo Basas as he claimed that despite the pandemic issues and concerns, he said that teachers are always ready to do their duties and responsibilities. He added that as he has said in the past that as long as the safety of school personnel and learners is ensured, these dedicated teachers will gladly comply as they are patiently doing different tasks, virtual and physical even during the Community Quarantine period.

As a whole, the readiness among teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 is verbally interpreted as "Highly Ready "as reflected by the overall mean of 3.46. This means that these teachers are always ready to perform their duties and responsibilities despite the COVID-19 pandemic.

Specific Question No.2 What are the problems encountered by the teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19?

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**Table 2
Problems Encountered by teachers on the Opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to CoVid-19**

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1	There is no solid/well-founded plan of actions initiated by the school head in ensuring the health and safety of teachers in the distribution of modules and to perform their duties in the new normal set-up.	1.38	Not A Problem At All	8
2	The school has no proper coordination and communication to the parents and other stakeholders regarding the new normal set-up.	1.43	Not A Problem At All	7
3	The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) are not feasible	1.33	Not A Problem At All	10
4	Lack of proper training and orientation regarding the utilization and execution of MELC.	1.47	Not A Problem At All	5.5
5	The teachers are at risk to be infected in the distribution of modules to the learners since there are no supplies of PPEs and face mask from the Department of Education.	2.58	Problem is Serious	3
6	The teacher's internet connection is not stable and not good enough to subscribe the online seminars (webinars) initiated by the Department of Education.	1.47	Not A Problem At All	5.5
7	There are times that the teacher's attention is compromised in watching webinars since there are tasks and paperworks to be accomplished first	2.63	Problem is Serious	2
8	The opening of School Year 2020-2021 is near but the modules are not yet distributed for us to study on how to deliver them effectively.	2.92	Problem is Serious	1
9	Some pupils did not enroll this School Year 2020-2021 because of the fear from the virus, hence the enrolment had decreased.	1.48	Not A Problem At All	4
10	The teacher is still confused on how to evaluate properly and effectively the learning and outputs of my pupils with the new normal set-up.	1.35	Not A Problem At All	9
	Average Weighted Mean	1.80	Problem is Slightly Serious	

Table 2 presents the weighted means, verbal interpretations, and ranks of the problems encountered by the teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021. As indicated in the table above, among ten categories, three of them had verbal interpretations as "Problem is Serious". Rank 1 is "The opening of School Year 2020-2021 is near but the modules are not yet distributed for us to study on how to deliver them effectively." with a weighted mean of 2.92. "There are times that the teacher's attention is compromised in watching webinars since there are tasks and paperwork to be accomplished first" ranked 2 with a weighted mean of 2.63. Ranked 3 is "The teachers are at risk to be infected in the distribution of modules to the learners since there are no supplies of PPEs and face mask from the Department of Education." With a weighted mean of 2.58.

On the other hand, seven categories had verbal interpretations of "Not a Problem At All" such as "Some pupils did not enroll this School Year 2020-2021

because of the fear from the virus, hence the enrolment had decreased." which is ranked 4 and with a weighted mean of 1.48. "Lack of proper training and orientation regarding the utilization and execution of MELC." and "The teacher's internet connection is not stable and not good enough to subscribe the online seminars (webinars) initiated by the Department of Education." both ranked 5.5 with a weighted mean of 1.47.

A weighted mean of 1.43 ranked 7 which is "The school has no proper coordination and communication to the parents and other stakeholders regarding the new normal set-up.". "There is no solid/well-founded plan of actions initiated by the school head in ensuring the health and safety of teachers in the distribution of modules and to perform their duties in the new normal set-up." ranked 8 with a weighted mean of 1.38. Ranked 9 is "The teacher is still confused about how to evaluate properly and effectively the learning and outputs of my pupils with the new normal set-up." with a weighted mean of 1.35. While "the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) are not feasible" ranked 10 with a weighted mean of 1.33. In general, the problems encountered by teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 had a weighted mean of 1.80 and verbally interpreted as "Problem is Slightly Serious".

Based on the data gathered, three indicators out of ten were found to be serious problems to the teachers on the opening of classes this School Year 2020-2021. First, the delayed distribution of the modules to the teachers for them to study and implement to the learners effectively. The findings of the study can be justifiable since on the interview last May 2020 in CNN Philippines, the Undersecretary of the Department of Education, Mr. Diosdado San Antonio, stressed that the preparation and printing of the printed modules are still on the process since schools today brace for major changes due to COVID-19 pandemic. Second, is the teachers' time that should be allotted in subscribing and watching webinars is being compromised since they have to finish first some reports/tasks to be submitted first. The result is supported by Ahrens, et.al as cited by White (2019) who stressed that there are disadvantages in utilizing webinars apart from the internet connection such as the sessions require all the participants to be on-line at an agreed time regardless of other tasks of participants may be. Further, for the participants, time differences and availability issues resulted in the diversion of their attention to the content of the webinar itself. And third, the lack of supply of Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs) and masks to the teachers since they will be having a physical visitation to their learners in handing out the modules which were being supported to the claim of the World Health Organization (2020) that those front-liners who are battling against the COVID-19 are having shortages and lack in terms of Personal Protective Equipment most especially the health workers across the globe. Hence, it can be inferred that the problem mentioned above as a result of the problem does not only occur in a certain area but rather in a worldwide set-up.

As a whole, the problems encountered by teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 is verbally interpreted as "Problem is Slightly Serious "as reflected by the overall mean of 1.80. This means that these problems like the delayed distribution

of the modules to the teachers for them to study and implement to the learners effectively, the teachers' time that should be allotted in subscribing and watching webinars is being compromised due to some reports/tasks to be submitted first and the lack of supply of Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs) and masks to the teachers were found to be a problem to the teachers as the School Year 2020-2021 is about to start.

Specific Question No. 3: Is there a significant difference in the teachers' readiness and the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19?

Table 3 Correlations between Readiness and Problems Encountered by the Teachers

Scores Paired	Coefficient of Correlation r	Level of Significance	Interpretation	Decision
Teachers Readiness Vs Problems Encountered	0.48	0.05	With Significant Difference	Reject Ho

Scale: Range of Values

$\pm 0.90 - 1.00$ Very high correlation; very dependable relationship

$\pm 0.70 - 0.89$ High correlation; marked relationship

$\pm 0.40 - 0.69$ Moderate correlation; substantial relationship

$\pm 0.20 - 0.39$ Low correlation; definite but small relationship

Less than ± 0.20 Negligible correlation

The computed coefficient correlation or r-value was 0.48 which signified a considerable moderate correlation. Therefore, the teachers' readiness registered a relationship with the problems they encountered.

Hence, the findings rejected the null hypothesis. This only means that there is a significant relationship between the teachers' readiness with the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year.

This finding was supported by Malipot (2020), who reported that a teachers' group expressed their support to the proposed revision of the school calendar in the Philippines, noting that no matter how ready these teaching personnel may be, there are still problems that will arise. Hence, as stated in his report, the authorities may find to move the opening of classes and to determine the date of opening of classes during the times of emergency such as the COVID-19 pandemic. With this, Teachers' Dignity Coalition National Chairperson Benjo Basas quoted that *"The reality is, we are not prepared or perhaps we need a little more time to prepare"*.

Specific Question No. 4. Based on the findings of this action research, what Intervention Scheme may be designed for the teachers in Binulasan Integrated School?

9. Proposed Intervention Program

9.1 Introduction

This teachers' readiness and problems encountered Intervention scheme was inspired from the 1987 Constitution of the Philippines, Section 1 Article 14 which mandates that "the state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels" and section 2 of Republic Act No. 10533 otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 which states that "the State shall establish, maintain and support a complete, adequate and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people, the country and society-at-large". Hence, teachers play a vital role in realizing these provisions to provide quality education to all.

On the same note, DepEd Order No. 42, series of 2017 otherwise known as the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers which states that "Teachers play a crucial role in nation-building. Through quality teachers, the Philippines can develop holistic learners who are steeped in values, equipped with 21st-century skills, and able to propel the country to development and progress" Hence, enhancing teacher quality becomes of utmost importance for long-term and sustainable nation-building.

However, these provisions in the 21st-century education seem to be challenged since most governments around the world have temporarily closed educational institutions in an attempt to contain the spread of the CoVid-19 pandemic. (UNESCO, 2020)

In a separate statement, UNESCO (2020), stated that in such unprecedented and uncertain times, it is normal for people to experience a higher level of stress and anxiety, including the teachers. They further said that teachers need supports to face the extra pressure being put on them to deliver learning in a time of crisis as well as support their students' needs. Hence, it is very important to assess the teachers' readiness in providing quality education to the learners.

Readiness and problems/constraints encountered by the teachers will definitely affect the way they handle their part in this new normal due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on the findings, the teachers are ready in doing their duties and responsibilities despite the above-mentioned pandemic. However, the delayed distribution of the modules to the teachers for them to study and implement to the learners effectively, teachers' time that should be allotted in subscribing and watching webinars is being compromised since they have to finish first some reports/tasks to be submitted first and the lack of supply of Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs) and masks to the teachers were the most pressing problems of the teachers in Binulasan Integrated School.

After the assessment of the teachers' readiness and the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19, the intervention program has been designed.

Finally, the successful implementation of this intervention scheme needs the strong cooperation and support of the school head, parents as well as to the teachers themselves to facilitate the enhancement of their efficiency by addressing the problems they encountered on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to COVID-19 pandemic.

9.2 General Objective

This Intervention scheme is designed to address the problems encountered by teachers in Binulanan Integrated School on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The Proposed Intervention Scheme

Problem	Specific Objective	Strategy	Persons Involved	Materials Needed	Specific Date	Expected Output	Budget
1. Delayed Distribution of Printed Modules	To help the teachers generate and formulate their lesson exemplars and other effective teaching materials while waiting for the release of the printed modules.	Maximize and utilize the expertise of the Master Teacher in training and developing the teachers in formulating their own lesson exemplars and other effective teaching materials which will be anchored on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) given by the Department of Education.	-Teachers -School Head -Master Teacher	Laptop, Projector	August 3-7, 2020	Teachers with a thorough knowledge on how to formulate their own lesson exemplars and other teaching materials to be used under the new normal	P 5,000
2. Teachers time that should be allotted in subscribing and watching webinars is being compromised since they have to finish first some paperworks and other teaching related tasks.	To develop a good time management practice among teachers.	The school head may include this matter during the conduct of Learning Action Cell (LAC) session with an emphasis on Time Management. In addition, the teachers should create a daily routine plan to help them monitor and budget their time in accomplishing their varied curricular and extra-curricular tasks. Equally important tasks should be planned and prioritized in terms of need.	-School Head -Teachers	Laptop, Projector	August 10, 2020	Proficient teachers in planning their desired goals with good time management skills.	P 5,000
3. Lack of supply of Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs) and masks to the teachers during the distribution of the modules (house to house)	To educate the teachers in providing knowledge regarding the other alternatives apart from wearing of PPEs in the distribution of modules.	Invite an expert from the Municipal Health Office of Infanta, Quezon to give a one-day seminar-workshop to the teachers in conducting a house to house distribution of modules to the learners in a safe way following the health standards from the Department of Health and Inter-agency Task Force's recommendations.	-Teachers -School Head -Health Expert from MHO	Laptop, Projector and handouts	August 13, 2020	Teachers who are knowledgeable in performing their duties and responsibilities in the new normal in a safe manner.	P 5,000

10. Summary, conclusions, and recommendations

This chapter presents a summary of the findings, conclusions, and recommendations. The Summary of the Findings follows the order of the Specific Questions in Chapter 1.

10.1 Summary of Findings

10.1.1 Teachers' Readiness

The readiness among teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 is verbally interpreted as "Highly Ready" as reflected by the overall mean of 3.46.

10.1.2 Problems Encountered by teachers

The problems encountered by teachers on the opening of School Year 2020-2021 is verbally interpreted as "Problem is Slightly Serious "as reflected by the overall mean of 1.80.

10.1.3 Relationship of Teachers' Readiness with the Problems They Encountered

The computed coefficient correlation or r-value was 0.48 which signified a considerable moderate correlation. Therefore, the teachers' readiness registered a relationship with the problems they encountered.

11. Conclusions

Based on the foregoing findings the following conclusions had been derived:

1. Teachers in Binulasan Integrated School possessed a positive outlook on their teaching profession as they claimed that they were ready to perform their duties and responsibilities under the new normal due to the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. Most of the problems encountered by the teachers were considered as not a problem at all. Except on the delayed distribution of the printed modules so they can study them first before they execute them effectively and efficiently to the learners. Also, teachers were having a hard time budgeting their time in doing their tasks while watching webinars given by the Department of Education. Lastly, teachers were unhappy about the lack of supply of Personal Protective Equipment and face masks since they will be conducting a house to house distribution of the modules to the learners.
3. The teachers' readiness registered a relationship with the problems they encountered as reflected in the computed coefficient correlation or r-value of 0.42 which signified a considerable moderate correlation. Hence, the findings rejected the null hypothesis. Therefore, one can determine that even the teachers feel that they are ready to perform their duties and responsibilities, still there are problems that they feel need to be addressed due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

12. Recommendations

In light of the aforementioned findings and conclusions, the following were hereby recommended:

1. The school head may tap and maximize the expertise of the Master Teacher in training and developing the teachers in formulating their own lesson exemplars and other effective teaching materials which will be anchored on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) given by the Department of Education under the new normal.
2. The school head may schedule the conduct of the Learning Action Cell (LAC) session with an emphasis on Time Management.
3. The teachers should create a daily routine plan to help them monitor and budget their time in accomplishing their varied curricular and extra-curricular tasks. Equally important tasks should be planned and prioritized in terms of need.

4. The School head must invite an expert from the Municipal Health Office of Infanta, Quezon to give a one-day seminar to the teachers in conducting a house to house distribution of modules to the learners in a safe way following the health standards from the Department of Health and Inter-agency Task Force's recommendations.
5. For future researchers, they could replicate this study and do further investigation on the preparation and adjustment(during) as well as the problems encountered by teachers due to CoVid-19.

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